

FLARE ENERGY–DURATION RELATIONS AT DIFFERENT EVOLUTIONARY STAGES

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It is generally believed that flares on late-type giant stars originate via similar physical processes and differ only by a scale factor in the energy levels from those observed on magnetically active dwarf stars. In this context, a generalized linear scaling for the logarithmic relation of flare energy and duration with a universal slope of $\approx 1/3$ can be derived on a theoretical basis. We study this in more detail by looking for flaring giants ($\log g \leq 3.5$) in the Kepler field. We created a database of ~ 4000 flares from the 61 flaring Kepler giants found. Based on the data, a simple generalized scaling between flare energies and their corresponding durations seems inappropriate because the logarithmic flare energy–duration relation is steeper for stars with lower surface gravity.

Flaring giants in the Kepler field

Historically, apart from the Sun, the first discovered flaring stars were lower main sequence (MS) and pre-MS stars. Although it was known from the beginnings that evolved stars also exhibit flares, the reported events were mostly incidental and their numbers were low, especially from photometry in the optical wavelengths. During their evolution stars spend much less time as giants with changing internal structure and energy production than on the MS, therefore the possible targets to study flaring activity is limited. The probable reasons of the scarcity of observed flares on giant stars are discussed in detail in [1], such as continuous monitoring is impossible from the Earth, the signal-to-noise ratio of the ground-based photometry is limited, flares are rare, and can hardly be seen as excess light above the high luminosity of the giant stars.

With the advent of high-precision space photometry, a brief summary about the flaring stars on the HRD was published in [2] based on *Kepler* long- and short-cadence observations. In [1] we studied the available long-cadence *Kepler* observations and found that the number of certainly flaring giants is 61 from the ≈ 700 giant candidates (with $\log g \leq 3.5$) in the *Kepler* field. The vast majority of stars on the giant branch were found to be oscillating stars, with only a few exceptions showing flares and oscillations at the same time.

In the present study, we start from the list of 86 flaring stars (of which 61 are giant) from the *Kepler* field, compiled in [1] (see their Sect. 3 for exact selection criteria). On the 86 stars a total of 4368 flare events were identified and analyzed as follows.

Deriving flare characteristics

To study the characteristics of the flares, we first extracted one-day-long regions around each flare peak. Then we fitted the quiescent flux variation with a low order polynomial. After subtracting this trend, shifting the peak time to zero, and scaling the flux by the flare peak, we fitted each flare with the analytical template of [3], leaving only the $t_{1/2}$ time scale as free parameter, which is the width of the template at half maximum, an easily measurable proxy of the flare duration characterizing the impulsive phase of the flare; see [4]. We then scaled each flare with the fitted $t_{1/2}$, and linearly interpolated them to a uniform time grid of 200 bins from $-3 t_{1/2}$ to $10 t_{1/2}$. An example for the flare extraction can be seen in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: Left: the original dataset with the cyan line showing the polynomial fitted to the rest region. Right: the extracted flare, with the template used to scale the time (red line). Black points show the original data points, and light blue points show the interpolated light curve.

To investigate the correlation between flare energy and flare duration, we took the raw integrated flare area (equivalent duration) and the fitted flare duration values (this latter marked by τ , i.e. the difference between fitted flare start and end times) from [1], as the output of the FLATWRM flare finding tool; see [5]. Flare energies were calculated by multiplying the equivalent duration of each flare with the quiescent luminosity of the corresponding host star in the *Kepler* bandpass. To calculate the quiescent luminosities, we convolved BT-NextGen [6] model spectra with the transmission curve of *Kepler*, similar to the treatment in [7]. Then, by integrating over the whole wavelength range, the ratio of the *Kepler* band and bolometric luminosities can be calculated. So for each star we used a model spectrum with the corresponding T_{eff} and $\log g$, and then used the bolometric luminosity of the star to get the quiescent luminosity in the *Kepler* band. All these astrophysical parameters, along with M masses, R radii and $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ metallicity values were taken from [8], a homogeneous catalog of fundamental parameters of *Kepler* stars, based on Gaia DR2 parallaxes. The stellar and flare parameters are given in Tables 1-2, respectively, in [9].

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Duration of flares on dwarfs and giants

We searched for connections between the flare time scale parameter $t_{1/2}$ and astrophysical parameters of the stars. The resulting diagrams are shown in Fig. 2. The upper left panel shows a strong correlation between the median $t_{1/2}$ of stars with $\log g$. While L , R and $\log g$ show strong correlations with $t_{1/2}$, the correlations with T_{eff} , M and $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ are only weak or moderate. The formal Spearman correlation coefficients and p-values are given in [9].

Figure 2: The change of $t_{1/2}$ flare duration proxy with $\log g$ surface gravity, L luminosity, R radius, T_{eff} effective temperature, M mass and $[\text{Fe}/\text{H}]$ metallicity, for the *Kepler* 30-min sample of flaring stars from [1]. Each dot represents the median $t_{1/2}$ value of the observed flares for a given star, while the corresponding dot size is proportional to the number of flares, with the scale shown in the upper left panel. The gray lines and the background shades show the running median and the 16th to 84th percentiles, respectively.

The left panel of Fig. 3 shows the relationship between the E_{Kepler} flare energy and the τ flare duration for stars with at least 10 flares in a log-log plot. The linear fits to the data of individual stars suggest an overall non-linear picture, namely, the slopes of the fits look steeper for stars that show higher energy flares, in this case, the giants. Indeed, the slopes of the fitted logarithmic energy–duration functions show a moderate correlation with $\log g$ with a Spearman correlation coefficient of -0.58 with $p = 1.4 \cdot 10^{-6}$; see Fig. 3 right panel.

Figure 3: Left: τ flare duration values for flares in the *Kepler* 30-min sample as a function of flare energy on a log-log scale with linear fits to the values of individual stars (having at least 10 flares). The $\log g$ values are represented by the color scale on the side. Right: slopes of the fitted lines from the left panel as a function of $\log g$. Error bars show the uncertainties of the slopes, the point sizes represent the number of flares observed on each star. The red line shows a linear fit.

Summary and conclusion

A homogeneous dataset of flares on giants and dwarfs in the *Kepler* field based on data with 30-min cadence was analyzed with the goal to find a general picture of flaring giants and the properties of their flares. Our result in Fig. 3 shows that the observed $\tau - E$ relation is not the same for stars in different evolutionary stages. It is likely that instead of the universal scaling law for the flare energy–duration of $\tau \propto E^{1/3}$ [10] for solar and stellar flares, another relationship applies for the superflaring giants. The generalized scaling law above can only be used under the assumption that the Alfvén velocity around the flaring region is more or less the same for the solar-type stars and it is unlikely to be the case for the superflaring giants; see the Alfvén velocity dependent scaling law suggested in [11]. The actual exponent of E in the observed $\tau - E$ relation depend on the wavelength of the data and also on the method how the flare energies were calculated and the flare lengths determined. See also the discussions in [11].

A simple scaling between flare energies and their corresponding durations seems inappropriate, since the logarithmic flare energy–duration relation is steeper for stars with lower surface gravity. We came to the conclusion that this discrepancy cannot be explained by higher frequency complex flares on giant stars. Therefore, we need to suppose that instead of the general scaling law of $\tau \propto E^{1/3}$ a slightly different scaling should be applied for superflaring giant stars. In other words, the universal scaling should be modified by introducing surface gravity dependency.

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